

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute
www.ejppri.eg.net

Efficacy of *Piper nigrum* black pepper fruit extract against two dangerous pests of stored grain insects *Tribolium confusum* and *Sitophilus granaries* (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae : Curculionidae)

Ahmed, El-Morsy Ali Hussein

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO Abstract

Article History

Received: 8/10/2025

Accepted: 23/11/2025

Keywords

Tribolium,
Sitophilus,
chemical
extraction, black
pepper and
bioassay.

Petroleum ether extract of black pepper fruits, *Piper nigrum* L, was evaluated in four concentrations for their toxicity effects against two major pests of stored grain insects, the adult confused flour beetle, *Tribolium confusum* (Jacquelin du Val) and *Sitophilus granarius* (L) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae : Curculionidae), the adult wheat weevil. The results obtained revealed that the mortality increased with increasing concentrations towards all target pests. The adult confused flour beetle was more susceptible than the wheat weevil. The mortality percentage reached 96.6% at a concentration 3% (w/w) after 14 days of treatment, while that of adult wheat weevil was 95.8%, and the LC₅₀ values for both adult pests were 1.38 and 2.022, respectively. The reduction in F₁ progeny in all treatments was greatly significant and was higher than the mortality in low concentrations, ranging from 60.5% to 100% according to the concentration and insect. By using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS) analysis, functional groups and compounds in the crude were determined, and the main constituents that may cause mortality, as well as their structures, formulae, and percentages. The main components were monoterpenes, Sesquiterpenes, fatty acids, and alkaloids, and some of the effective constituents were α -pinene, linalool, α -copaene, linoleic acid, and piperine.

Introduction

Some insect pests cause serious damage to stored grains by feeding and developing inside kernels. Some other insect pest species hide and feed inside cracked grains, causing their detection to be more difficult, while some others feed on broken and fine grains (Satya *et al.*, 1996). The presence of these pests in grains caused cash discounts by affecting the quality, quantity, and commercial value of grains (Santos *et al.*, 1990), because of the effects of

damage on quality and quantity, making no demand for the products. Many stored product pests belong to the order Coleoptera, which are considered the most destructive, although they're a secondary pest, insect pests of stored products include the confused flour beetle, *Tribolium confusum* (Jacquelin du Val) (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). The stored grain infestation by these serious insect pests has been damaging the economy and is responsible for a

worldwide loss of 10-40% annually (Matthews, 1993).

It is found that many plant extracts have been evaluated for their toxic and other effective properties against a wide range of stored products and grain insect pests, especially in oils, crudes, and essential oil forms (Ngamo *et al.*, 2007). The application of insecticides and fumigants was the commonly used method for controlling the stored product pests (Chaubey, 2008). But now, without any doubt, synthetic insecticides cause various hard problems for the environment, living beings, and human health. For example, the side effects of these insecticides are neurotoxic to humans as well as domestic animals. This fact leads us towards using the application of natural extracts as an insecticide, such as crude and essential oils from botanical sources, as an alternative means instead of chemical insecticides. The natural insecticides derived from plant extractions were evaluated by many researchers for their insecticidal properties (Tooba *et al.*, 2005; Iqbal *et al.*, 2010, and Sarwar and Sattar, 2012). Also, it was proved that natural insecticides are mostly safe, excellent, and have no environmental damage effects when applied in the right ways against various insects and pests (Isman, 2006; Tripathi *et al.*, 2009, and Sarwar *et al.*, 2013).

Today, attention has been focused on controlling stored products and grain pests by using alternative agents like plant extracts from leaves, flowers, seeds, or the whole plant (Su, 1985 and Halawa *et al.*, 2009). In addition, the extracts of some medical plants are beneficial and safely used for human beings (Nawaz, 1999). The confused flour beetle *T. confusum* and the wheat weevil, or granary weevil, *Sitophilus granarius* (L) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) are the most abundant and injurious pests of stored products

and grains. They were found in flour mills and warehouses in warm and tropical regions all over the world (Semple, 1986; Rees, 2004, and Beckett *et al.*, 2007). Also, the need for safe and natural control methods as an alternative to chemical pesticides is a major concern for human health and environments (Kostyukovsky *et al.*, 2002). Now, many investigations have been carried out on extracts of black pepper fruits, *piper nigrum*, revealing that they have great potency as an efficient insecticide towards a wide range of insects and pests (Khani *et al.*, 2012 and Ashouri and Shayesteh, 2009).

This study aims to assess the efficacy of black pepper fruit extracts against two serious and dangerous stored grain insect pests; one of them is a secondary pest, the confused flour beetle, *T. confusum*, and the other is the primary pest, the granary weevil, *S. granarius*. An analysis by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS) was performed to estimate the main chemical constituents of black pepper fruit extracts.

Materials and methods

1. Insect culture maintenance:

The two pest insects that were being tested were obtained from warehouses and some infected mills, transported to the lab, and raised to be kept in two different cultures. They were raised in ideal circumstances of $28\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $65\pm 5\%$ RH and were fed on sterilized wheat for *S. granarius* and on sterilized flour mill for *T. confusum*. For a few months, the population density of the two insect pest cultures increased by placing them in suitable, clean glass jars with muslin-covered mouths. In order to keep the cultures healthy and clean before the studies, susceptible strains for treatments were developed, and the medium was replaced.

2. Crude extraction:

Using an electric grinder, the clean, dried black pepper fruits were ground

into a fine powder; 500 g of the fine powder were continuously stirred for 3 days while being soaked in 1 liter of petroleum ether in a 2-liter dark glass jar (Su, 1985). A piece of gauze was used first to filter the solution before it was passed three times through filter paper to produce a clear solution. The resulting solution was evaporated at 50°C in a rotary evaporator, and the residue was weighed and stored at 4°C until use. In the same solvent, the extracted crude was dissolved to create a 10% (w/w) stock solution, which was then diluted to create 0.75%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5% solutions.

3. Bioassay:

The two tested pest insects, *S. granarius* and *T. confusum*, were used to test and determine the toxicity of black pepper fruit extract. In a 50 ml petri dish for each concentration, ten grams of sterilized flour mill, in the case of *T. confusum*, and sterilized wheat grains, in the case of *S. granarius*, were mixed with 0.75%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5% (w/w) concentrations of the petroleum ether extract of black pepper fruits. After being exposed to air for 24 hours, the treated media in each petri dish had completely dried out of the petroleum ether solvent. For each concentration of treated media in each petri dish, 30 individuals of each adult stage of *T. confusum* and *S. granarius* were separately placed. Four replicates of each concentration were tested, and the conditions were maintained under control in a lab incubator at 28±1°C and 65±5% RH. In order to prepare the positive control tests, media that included only solvent and no crude extract were utilized; four replicates of each pest insect were also employed, but only after the solvent had completely dried out. The untreated media alone, without the use of any solvent or crude extract, were used to prepare the negative control experiments. The mortality values of the tested pest

insects were recorded after 1, 2, 3, 5, 7, 10, and 14 days of exposure. After 45 days of media incubation following the isolation of the adults from treated media of each concentration, the number of F1, or first-generation progeny, was also counted; the percentage of offspring decrease was then computed.

4. Data analysis:

The correction of the mortality percentages was carried out by using Abbott (1925). The reduction of offspring percentage was calculated according to the equation of El-Lakwah *et al.*, (1996). The mortality percentages were analyzed by using the probit ANOVA test using a Minitab computer program to determine the P-value. The mean values were adjusted according to Duncan's Multiple Range test (Duncan, 1951) at 0.01 and 0.05 significance levels, also by using LDP-line software to estimate the LC₅₀, LC₉₀, slope values, and toxicity index of the tested extracts (Finney, 1971).

5. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis:

The chemical constituents of the petroleum ether black pepper fruit crude extracts were identified by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS) at the Central Pesticides Laboratory, Dokki, Giza, Egypt. The compound identification was done by comparing NIST and WILEY libraries with the authentic spectra (Adams, 1995), and the data of peaks reported in literature. The constituent percents were computed using GC peak areas on BP-I column without applying correction factors.

Results and discussion

1. Toxicological findings:

1.1. Confused flour beetle:

The data in Table (1) demonstrated an increase in the recorded mortality values with the increase of the applied concentrations and exposure duration in most treatments. After 14 days of exposure to 0.75%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5% concentrations (w/w) of petroleum ether black pepper fruit

extract, the mortality rate of adult flour beetles *T. confusum* was 70.8%, 83.3%, 96.6%, and 100%, respectively, with a p-value 0.013. Additionally, these treatments resulted in a reduction in F1 progeny of 70.5%, 82.3%, 95.5%, and 100% at

concentrations of 0.75%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5% (w/w), respectively, of petroleum ether black pepper fruit extract. The LC₅₀ value was 1.38, and the toxicity index was 100%, as shown in Table (3) and Figure (1).

Table (1): Toxicity of pepper fruit extract against adult *Tribolium confusum*.

Conc. (w/w) %	Adult mortality % after indicated days (<i>Tribolium confusum</i>)							% R. in F ₁ progeny
	1	2	3	5	7	10	14	
0.75%	0.8±1.1 ^a	5±1.1 ^b	10.8±1.8 ^b	20±1.5 ^c	28.3±2.5 ^b	40±4.1 ^b	70.8±8.3 ^b	70.5%
1.5%	1.6±1.1 ^a	6.6±1.5 ^b	14.1±1.8 ^{ab}	23.3±1.5 ^{bc}	31.6±2.4 ^b	42.5±3.6 ^b	83.3±9.8 ^{ab}	82.3%
3%	2.5±0.9 ^a	10±1.5 ^{ab}	17.5±1.8 ^a	26.6±1.5 ^{ab}	35±2.4 ^b	69.1±8.1 ^a	96.6±2.7 ^a	95.5%
5%	4.1±0.9 ^a	13.3±1.5 ^a	20.8±1.8 ^a	30±1.5 ^a	75±3.3 ^a	85.8±6.5 ^a	100±0 ^a	100%
P-Value	0.217	0.003	0.003	0.001	0.000	0.000	0.013	
Control	0±0							

1.2. Granary weevil:

In most treatments, it is observed that the data in Table (2) likewise demonstrated an increase in the recorded mortality values as the applied concentrations and exposure period increased. The mortality rates of adult granary weevil *S. granarius* were 68.3%, 84.1%, 95.8%, and 100% at concentrations of 0.75%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5% (w/w), respectively, after 14 days of

exposure to petroleum ether black pepper fruit extract, with a p-value of 0.000. Additionally, at concentrations of 0.75%, 1.5%, 3%, and 5% (w/w) of petroleum ether black pepper fruit extract, these treatments led to a reduction in F1 progeny of 60.5%, 81.2%, 95.5%, and 100%, respectively. As shown in Table (2). The LC₅₀ value was 2.022, and the toxicity index was 68.2%, according to Table (3) and Figure (1).

Table (2): Toxicity of black pepper fruit extract against adult *Sitophilus granarius*.

Conc. (w/w) %	Adult mortality after indicated days (<i>Sitophilus granarius</i>)							% R. in F ₁ progeny
	1	2	3	5	7	10	14	
0.75%	15±4.5 ^b	17.5±5.4 ^b	26.6±3.4 ^b	30±3.4 ^b	38.3±4.5 ^b	55±6.5 ^b	68.3±2.4 ^c	60.5%
1.5%	20±3.4 ^b	25±4.5 ^b	29.1±3.9 ^b	34.1±3.9 ^b	41.6±4.5 ^b	60±5.6 ^b	84.1±2.3 ^b	81.2%
3%	26.6±2.7 ^b	31.6±2.4 ^b	34.3±2.8 ^b	40±3.4 ^b	46.6±3.4 ^b	66.6±4.1 ^b	95.8±2.8 ^a	95.5%
5%	44.1±2.3 ^a	49.3±1.8 ^a	52.5±1.7 ^a	61.6±2.4 ^a	73.3±4.1 ^a	95±2.4 ^a	100±0 ^a	100%
P-Value	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	
Control	0±0							

Table (3): LC₅₀ values of black pepper fruits extract against the target insects.

Pt. Ether Extract	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Slope	Toxicity index (%)
<i>Tribolium confusum</i>	1.38	8.643	1.608	100
<i>Sitophilus granarius</i>	2.022	41.328	0.978	68.249

Figure (1): Toxicity line of black pepper fruits extract against the target insects.

2. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis:

By comparing the peaks and mass spectra of the petroleum ether fraction of the black pepper fruits, *P. nigrum* L., with those of their analogous reported by NIST and WILEY libraries, as well as with the authentic spectra, the GC/MS chromatography analysis showed that the chemical constituents of the fraction were identified and characterized. Determining the peak name, the percentage amount, the formula, the component structures, and the classification into their classes were all part of the analysis. Numerous functional groups and components were discovered and categorized into several classes, including monoterpenes, sesquiterpenes, acetogenins (fatty acids or derivatives), alkaloids, and miscellaneous components. Terpenes, which are formed biosynthetically from isoprene units and have a basic chemical formula of C_5H_8 and their numerous linked isoprene units (C_5H_8)_n, are the main constituents of many

plants essential oils. Sesquiterpenes are made up of three isoprene units and have the formula $C_{15}H_{24}$; diterpenes are made up of four isoprene units and have the formula $C_{20}H_{32}$; and triterpenes are made up of six isoprene units and have formula $C_{30}H_{48}$. Ten monoterpenes, six sesquiterpenes, five acetogenins (Fatty derivatives), one alkaloid compound, and one miscellaneous compound were identified as the primary twenty-three compounds found in the petroleum ether fraction of black pepper fruit extracts using GC/MS analysis, as shown in Table (4).

The percentages and mass spectra of major compounds were α -pinene (1.5%), sabinene (3.21%), γ -terpinene (1.92%), 3-carene (4.89%), linalool (0.76%), carvone (0.5%), α -copaene (8.5%), α -zingiberene (13.36%), α -humulene (1.73%), α -elemene (3.94%), δ -cadinene (4.82%), aromadendrene (2.07%), linoleic acid (2.79%), docosane (2.92%), and piperine (2.71%). All data were recorded in Table (4) and Figures (2-9).

Table (4): Main components identified by Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis of petroleum ether black pepper fruits extract.

No.	Peak Name	Formula	M.W.	RT (min)	Area (%)
1	(R)- α -pinene	$C_{10}H_{16}$	136.2340	5.176	1.51
2	Sabinene	$C_{10}H_{16}$	136.2340	6.254	3.21
3	γ -Terpinene	$C_{10}H_{16}$	136.2340	7.120	1.92
4	3-Carene	$C_{10}H_{16}$	136.2340	7.782	4.89
5	Terpinolene	$C_{10}H_{16}$	136.2340	9.530	0.36
6	2-Carene	$C_{10}H_{16}$	136.2340	10.108	0.98
7	Linalool	$C_{10}H_{18}O$	154.2493	11.432	0.76
8	trans-Sabinenhydrate	$C_{10}H_{18}O$	154.2493	13.614	1.08
9	trans-Dihydrocarvone	$C_{10}H_{16}O$	152.2334	14.021	1.00
10	Carvone	$C_{10}H_{14}O$	150.2176	15.108	0.50
11	α -Copaene	$C_{15}H_{24}$	204.3511	17.671	8.50
12	α -Zingiberene	$C_{15}H_{24}$	204.3511	18.766	13.36
13	α -Humulene	$C_{15}H_{24}$	204.3511	20.778	1.73
14	α -Elemene	$C_{15}H_{24}$	204.3511	21.602	3.94
15	δ -Cadinene	$C_{15}H_{24}$	204.3511	22.111	4.82
16	(+)-Aromadendrene	$C_{15}H_{24}$	204.3511	23.758	2.07
17	(2E,4Z)-N-Isobutyl-2,4-decadienamide	$C_{14}H_{25}$	223.354	32.697	4.31
18	1-Eicosene	$C_{20}H_{40}$	280.5316	36.372	0.84
19	Linoleic acid	$C_{18}H_{32}O_2$	280.4455	37.034	2.79
20	Eicosene	$C_{20}H_{42}$	282.5475	37.985	0.66
21	Docosane	$C_{22}H_{46}$	310.6006	39.717	2.92
22	Tricosane	$C_{23}H_{48}$	324.6272	40.150	0.72
23	Piperine	$C_{17}H_{19}NO_3$	285.3377	45.634	2.71

Figure (2): Mass spectrum of (R)- α -pinene.

Figure (3): Mass spectrum of γ -terpinene.

Figure (4): Mass spectrum of linalool.

Figure (5): Mass spectrum of carvone.

Figure (6): Mass spectrum of α -zingiberene.

Figure (7): Mass spectrum of α -humulene.

Figure (8): Mass spectrum of (+)-aromadendrene.

Figure (9): Mass spectrum of piperine.

The mortality percentages in this study demonstrated that exposure time and concentration were related to the rise in mortality across all tests. The adult confused flour beetle was the most susceptible, followed by the granary weevil. The mortality findings of the treatment with petroleum ether extract were higher than those of the controls. Particularly at low concentrations, the decrease in F1 progeny was greater than

the mortality. The insecticidal properties of certain of the oil's constituents, including α -pinene, linalool, carvone, α -copaene, linoleic acid, and piperine, were responsible for the significant mortality rates in the majority of treatments.

The findings of this study were almost identical to those of the toxicity of garlic oil extract against *T. confusum* eggs, larvae, and adults, as well as

Sitophilus zeamais adults (Ho *et al.*, 1996). They discovered that *T. confusum* egg mortality rose with oil concentration, with eggs being the most susceptible stage, followed by adults and older larvae. Adult confused flour beetles were more susceptible to garlic oil than *S. zeamais* adults, and they were unable to produce F1 offspring.

Additionally, research on the effects of acetonic extracts of black pepper, dill, and cumin on cowpea beetles showed that the black pepper was the most effective in terms of mortality, repellency, reduction in F1 progeny, oviposition rates, and hatchability ratios (El-Lakwah and Mohamed, 1998). The grain weevil and confused flour beetle were tested for the toxic effects of petroleum ether extract of cumin seeds and 99.8% N₂. The results revealed high adult mortality values at the highest concentration of 10% of cumin seed extract in two weeks after treatment, while very low mortality with *T. confusum* and suppression in F1 progeny was higher than mortality (El-Lakwah *et al.*, 2001).

When petroleum ether extracts of black pepper fruits, dill seeds, and clove fruits were tested against the confused flour beetle *T. confusum*, the results showed a low adult mortality after 7 days of treatment with a reduction in F1 progeny higher than the mortality percentage; however, the toxicity effect of extracts under phosphine treatment was higher than for each extract alone (Mohamed, 2001). When *Piper nigrum* essential oil was tested for its repellent, insecticidal, and developmental inhibitory properties against *T. confusum* adults and larvae, it was discovered that mortality rose as concentration increased while larval survival and adult emergence fell (Upadhyay and Jaiswal, 2007).

When the insecticidal properties of red and black pepper fruit powders were tested against *S. granaries*, the results

showed that both extracts completely reduced the number of F1 progeny and that black pepper caused a higher mortality rate than red pepper (Ashouri and Shayesteh, 2009). The effects of black pepper fruit seed powder on some biological aspects and *Trogoderma granarium* mortality were investigated. The findings indicated a high mortality rate, a high reduction in F1 progeny, a high potential for repellency, and a prolonged period of F1 adult emergence of the insect life cycle (Mhemed, 2011). GC/MS of black pepper was used to assess and identify the insecticidal activity of essential oils against adult *S. granarius* and third-instar granary moth larvae. The results showed that *S. granarius* is the most vulnerable (Khani *et al.* 2012).

The current study's identification results utilizing GC/MS analysis were in the same direction and highly consistent with the findings of another study that revealed over 80 components (Gopalakrishnan *et al.*, 1993). They examined 42 components of black pepper extract in yet another agreement study (Zachariah, 1995). Germacrene D (11.01%), limonene (10.26%), β -pinene (10.02%), α -phellandrene (8.56%), β -caryophyllene (7.29%), α -pinene (6.40%), and cis- β -ocimene (3.19%), were the main constituents of the essential oils of black pepper fruits, as demonstrated and identified by GC/MS analysis (Jirovetza *et al.*, 2002).

After analyzing and identifying the essential oils of *Piper nigrum*, thirty components were detected, with β -caryophyllene accounting for 23.49%, 3-carene for 22.20%, D-limonene for 18.68%, β -pinene for 8.92%, and α -pinene for 4.03%, Eugenol for 7.39%, D-limonene for 6.70%, Zingiberene for 6.68%, and Cubenol for 3.64% (Liu *et al.*, 2007). Using GC/MS to quantify the total percentages of essential oils from the two types of black pepper, it was discovered that the total monoterpenes

were 65.421% and the total sesquiterpenes were 34.579% (Aziz *et al.*, 2012).

According to the obtained results, *P. nigrum* oils showed strong potential toxicity effects on two serious and notorious insect pests of stored grains, the confused flour beetle *T. confusum* and granary weevil *S. granarius*, and could use these oils to protect the stored grains, which are non-toxic in handling and use. So that the studied oils have a high potential to suppress, struggle, lethal, and toxic effects on adults, and also on all developmental stages, causing a prolonged life cycles of these serious pests and considered a promising alternative source and safe natural insecticides or bio-insecticides.

References

- Abbott, W. J. (1925):** A method for computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 18: 265-276.
- Adams, R. P. (1995):** Textbook of identification of essential oil components gas chromatography/mass spectroscopy. 2nd ed., 46: 1460.
- Ashouri, Sh. and Shayesteh N. (2009):** Insecticidal activities of black pepper and red pepper in powder form on adults of *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.) and *Sitophilus granarius* (L.). *Pak. Entomol.*, 31(2): 122-127.
- Aziz, S.; Naher, Sh.; Abukawsar, M. D. and Roy, S. K. (2012):** Comparative studies on physicochemical properties and GC-MS analysis of essential oil of the two varieties of the black pepper (*Piper nigrum* Linn.). *Int. J. Pharm. Phytopharmacol. Res.*, 2(2): 67-70.
- Beckett, S.J., Fields, P.G. and Subramanyam, B. (2007):** Disinfestation of Stored Products and Associated Structures Using Heat. In: Tany, J., Mitcham, E., Wang, S. and Lurie, S., Eds., *Heat Treatments for Postharvest Pest Control: Theory and Practice*, CABI, 182-237. <https://doi.org/10.1079/9781845932527.0182>
- Chaubey, M. K. (2008):** Fumigant toxicity of essential oils from some common spices against pulse beetle, *Callosobruchus chinensis* (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *J. Oleo. Sci.*, 57(3):171-9. doi:10.5650/jos.57.171.
- Duncan, D. B. (1951):** A significance test for differences between ranked treatments in an analysis of variance. *Virginia J. Sci.*, 2(3): 171-189.
- El-Lakwah, F. A. and Mohamed, R. A. (1998):** Toxicity effect of some plant extracts against the cowpea beetle, *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.). *Annals of Agric. Sc.*, Moshtohor, 36(4): 2627-2635.
- El-Lakwah, F. A.; Mohamed, R. A. and Abd El-Aziz, A. E. (2001):** Toxicity and joint action of cumin seeds extract with certain controlled atmospheres against stored product insects. *Proc. Int. Conf. Controlled Atmosphere and Fumigation in Stored Products*, Fresno, CA. 29 Oct. - 3 Nov. 2000, Executive Print. Serv., Clovis, CA, U.S.A. pp. 133-147.
- El-Lakwah, F.A.; Darwish, A. A. and Halawa, Z. A. (1996):** Toxic effect of extracts and powders of some plants against the cowpea beetle (*Callosobruchus maculatus*, F.). *Annals-of-Agricultural-Science*, Moshtohor, 34(4): 1849-1859.
- Finney, D. J. (1971):** Probit analysis. *A Statistical Treatment of The Sigmoid Response Curve*. 7th Ed., Cambridge Univ. Press, England.
- Gopalakrishnan, M.; Menon, N.; Padmakumari, K. P.; Jayalakshmi, A. and Narayanan, C. S. (1993):** GC analysis and odor profiles of four new Indian Genotypes of *Piper nigrum* L. *Journal of Essential Oil Research*, 5(3): 247-253.

- <https://doi.org/10.1080/10412905.1993.9698217>
- Halawa, Z. A.; EL-Sappagh, I. A. and EL-Assal, M. M. (2009):** Toxicity of Toothpick Seed (*Ammi visnaga* L.) extracts against the lesser grain borer, *Rhizopertha dominica*, F. (Bostrychidae: Coleoptera) Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 88(2): 485-493. doi:10.21608/ejar.2010.186979
- Ho, S. H.; Koh, L.; Ma, Y.; Huang, Y. and Sim, K. Y. (1996):** The oil of garlic, *Allium sativum* L. (Amaryllidaceae), as a potential grain protectant against *Tribolium confusum* (Herbst) and *Sitophilus zeamais* Motsch. Postharvest Biology and Technology, 9(1): 41-48. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0925-5214\(96\)00018-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0925-5214(96)00018-X)
- Iqbal, J.; Jilani, G. and Aslam, M. (2010):** Growth inhibiting effects of plant extracts against the grain moth, *Sitotroga cerealella* (Oliv.) (Gelechiidae: Lepidoptera). Pak. J. Zool., 42(5): 597-601.
- Isman, M. B. (2006):** Botanical insecticides, deterrents, and repellents in modern agriculture and an increasingly regulated world. Annual Review of Entomology, 51: 45-66. doi:10.1146/annurev.ento.51.110104.151146
- Jirovetza, L.; Buchbauer, G.; Ngassoumb, M. B. and Geissler, M. (2002):** Aroma compound analysis of *Piper nigrum* and *Piper guineense* essential oils from Cameroon using solid-phase microextraction-gas chromatography, solid-phase microextraction-gas chromatography-mass spectrometry and olfactometry. Journal of Chromatography A, 976: 265-275. doi:10.1016/S0021-9673(02)00376-X.
- Khani, M.; Awang, R. M. and Omar, D. (2012):** Insecticidal effects of peppermint and black pepper essential oils against granary weevil, *Sitophilus granarius* L. and granary moth, *Corcyra cephalonica* (St.). J. Med. Plants., 11(43): 97-110.
- Kostyukovsky, M.; Rafaeli, A. and Gileadi, C. (2002):** Activation of octopaminergic receptors by essential oil constituents isolated from aromatic plants: possible mode of action against insect pests. Pest Management sci., 58(11): 1101-106. doi: 10.1002/ps.548.
- Liu, L.; Song, G. and Hu, Y. (2007):** GC-MS Analysis of the Essential Oils of *Piper nigrum* L. and *Piper longum* L. Chromatographia, 66: (9/10):785-790. <https://doi.org/10.1365/s10337-007-0408-2>
- Matthews, G. A. (1993):** Insecticide Application in the Stores. In Matthews, G.A. and Hislop, E.C. (eds.). Application Technology for Crop Protection. CAB, London, pp. 305-315.
- Mhemed, A. J. (2011):** The Efficacy of four seed powders on some biological aspects and mortality of Khapra beetle. Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences, 42(6): 112-123.
- Mohamed, R. A. (2001):** Efficacy of some plant extracts alone and under phosphine treatment against the confused flour beetle *Tribolium confusum* (Herbst). Annals of Agric. Sc., Moshtohor, 39(3): 1767-1777.
- Nawaz, A. (1999):** Appraisal of weight losses in stored grains by *Granariusphilus surinamensis* (L.) (Coleoptera: Cucujidae) and its mortality by plant extracts. M.Sc. (Hons) Thesis. Department of Entomology, NWFP Agricultural University.
- Ngamo, T. L.S.; Goudoum, A.; Ngassoum, M. B.; Mapongmetsen, P. M.; Lognay, G.; Malaisse, F. and Hance, T. (2007):** Chronic toxicity of essential oils of 3 local aromatic

- plants towards *Sitophilus zeamais* Motsch (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). Afr. J. Agri. Res., 2(4): 164-167.
- Rees, D. P. (2004):** (Ed.) Insects of Stored Products. Manson Publishing, Ltd., UK.
- Santos, J. P.; Maia, J. D. G. and Cruz, I. (1990):** Damage to germination of seed corn caused by maize weevil (*Sitophilus zeamais*) and Angoumois grain moth (*Sitotroga cerealella*). Pesquisa agropecuaria brasileira, 25(12): 1687-1692. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S163921.pab1990.v25.13718>
- Sarwar, M. and Sattar, M. (2012):** Appraisal of different plant products against *Trogoderma granarium* Everts to protect stored wheat a laboratory comparison. Nucleus, 49(1): 65-69. <https://doi.org/10.71330/thenucleus.2012.816>
- Sarwar, M.; Ashfaq, M.; Ahmad, A. and Randhawa, M. A. M. (2013):** Assessing the potential of assorted plant powders on survival of caloglyphus grain mite (Acari: Acaridae) in wheat grain. Int. J. Agric. Sci. Bioresour. Eng. Res., 2(1): 1-6.
- Satya, V.; Jindal, S. and Vir, S. (1996):** Field infestation of *Caryedon serratus* Olivier (Coleoptera: Bruchidae) on the pods and seeds of *Acacia nilotica* in the Thar desert of India. Journal of Tropical Forest Science, 9(2): 189-193.
- Sample, R. L. (1986):** Problems relating to pest control and use of pesticides in grain storage: The current situation in ASEAN and future requirements. Pesticides and Humid Tropical Grain Storage System: ACIAR Proc., 45-47.
- Su, H. C. F. (1985):** Laboratory study on effects of *Anethum graveolens* seeds on four species of stored product insects. J. Econ. Entomol., 78(2): 451-453. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/78.2.451>
- Tooba, H.; Usman, N. F. and Abbas, T. (2005):** Screening of plant leaves as grain protectants against *Tribolium confusum* during storage. Pak. J. Bot., 37(1): 149-53.
- Tripathi, A. K.; Upadhyay, S.; Bhuiyan, M. and Bhattacharya, P. R. (2009):** A review on the prospects of essential oils as biopesticides in insect pest-management. J. Pharmacognosy Phytotherapy, 1(15): 52-63.
- Upadhyay, R. K. and Jaiswal, G. (2007):** Evaluation of biological activities of *Piper nigrum* oil against *Tribolium confusum*. Bulletin of Insectology, 60(1): 57-61.
- Zachariah, J. (1995):** Essential oil and its major constituents in selected black pepper accessions. Plant Physiology and Biochemistry, New Delhi, 22(2): 151-153.